

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

GPNMB

(Glycoprotein non-metastatic B)

A Target Enabling Package (TEP)

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TREAT-AD Authors	Greg Cary ¹ , Paul Brennan ² , YCharOS ³ , and the Emory-Sage-SGC-JAX TREAT-AD Center
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Affiliations	¹ The Jackson Laboratory, Bar Harbor, ME, USA ² Alzheimer's Research UK Oxford Drug Discovery Institute, Centre for Medicines Discovery, University of Oxford, Oxford, UK ³ YCharOS, McGill University, Montreal, QC, Canada

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SUMMARY OF PROJECT

Glycoprotein non-metastatic B (GPNMB) is expressed in the brain as well as multiple other tissues ([Human Protein Atlas](#)) and may play cell type specific roles in neurodegeneration and Alzheimer's disease (AD) pathophysiology. The GPNMB project is focused upon the development of a target enabling package (TEP) that can stimulate the exploration of this potentially disease-linked protein in the broader scientific community. These resources include a bioinformatic analysis, the validation of antibodies for common applications, the generation of purified proteins, and future development of specific modulators of GPNMB for the advancement of future investigations into the link between GPNMB and AD by interested academic or industry investigators.

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

GPNMB is a type I transmembrane glycoprotein linked with Parkinson's disease (PD), Alzheimer's disease (AD), and frontotemporal dementia [1–5]. The role of GPNMB is not clear, yet multiple studies show that GPNMB is expressed in microglia and astrocytes in AD and PD [6,7]. GPNMB is cleaved in the perimembranous region by ADAM10, releasing the soluble ectodomain [7], which is reported to play a role in facilitating hippocampal synaptic plasticity [8]. GPNMB binds several microglia membrane proteins, including NKA, Syndecan-4, and CD44 [7], supporting a role in the regulation of the innate immune response. Consistently, GPNMB is found to regulate the proinflammatory behavior of both astrocytes and microglia in neurodegeneration [7,9,10]. Other studies suggest the involvement of GPNMB in the stimulation of autophagy to counteract AD-related amyloid aggregation [11]. Single cell analysis of AD versus control mouse microglia associate GPNMB with an MHC-II positive activated response microglia lineage in disease and ageing [12]. In line with this notion, GPNMB is found to increase over time in the brains of several transgenic mouse models of AD, and can be detected specifically co-localized with amyloid plaque-associated microglia in these models as well as in brain tissue from clinical cases of sporadic AD [13]. While the function of GPNMB in neurodegenerative disease is unclear, it appears plausible that it may regulate aspects of both inflammatory and phagocytic events in AD pathogenesis and progression.

Target Source & Hypothesis

The TREAT-AD Center has developed a target ranking score encompassing genomics and genetics evidence. The Target Risk Score represents the gene target’s general relevance to Alzheimer’s Disease, and is the sum of the target’s Genetics Score and Genomics Score. Target Risk Score values range from 0 to 5, with 5 being evidence of the strongest association with AD. A complete description of the methodology used to calculate these scores is available [here](#) [14]. This score was taken from Agora, Data Version syn13363290-v62.

The TREAT-AD Target Risk Score for GPNMB is 3.94 out of 5 (rank #476, 98th percentile) (**Fig. 1A**). The individual score components include 1.94 of 3 for genetics (87th percentile) (**Fig. 1B**), and 1.99 out of 2 for genomics (98th percentile) (**Fig. 1C**). The meta-analysis of proteomic and transcriptomic data sources used in the genomics score indicates that the expression of GPNMB, both protein and RNA, is significantly higher in brains from patients with AD.

Cell-type specific expression is assessed using single-cell data from the Seattle Alzheimer’s Disease Brain Cell Atlas (SEA-AD) (sea-ad.org, [15]). Gene expression was averaged across cells within a supertype from each donor. The locally weighted mean expression (LOWESS) of superotypes within each subclass is then plotted across the range of continuous donor pseudo-progression, which orders subjects based on a learned model of neuropathological burden. GPNMB is expressed primarily in OPC cell types from the SEA-AD dataset. GPNMB expression is stable within cell types subclasses across donor pseudo-progression (**Fig. 1D**).

Figure 1. (A) TREAT-AD Target Risk Score, and component (B) genetic risk score and (C) multi-omic risk score. The lines within the score and component score violin plots show the 50th and 90th percentile scores. (D) GPNMB cell type expression data from SEA-AD. Cell type expression plots show the locally weighted mean expression of cell superotypes from each donor within each subclass along donor pseudo-progression.

The TREAT-AD Center has also developed a target categorization system specific to AD relevant processes, termed biological domains (“biodomains”) [14]. These biodomains are defined by constituent Gene Ontology

(GO) terms and genes are then annotated to specific biodomains via GO term annotations. GPNMB is annotated to GO terms from 5 biodomains, primarily to terms from the Immune Response, Vasculature, and Cell Cycle domains (**Fig. 2A**).

The CRISPRbrain resource (crisprbrain.org, [16]) is a data commons for functional genomics datasets from differentiated human iPSC derived cell types. The resource reports phenotype results following CRISPR screens of gene activation (CRISPRa), inhibition (CRISPRi), or gene knockout (CRISPRn), in iPSC derived brain-relevant cell types. Following the screens, genes are identified as either positive or negative hits, meaning perturbation leads to a significant and reproducible increase or decrease in the measured phenotype, respectively, or a non-hit if the perturbation does not significantly impact the phenotype. GPNMB is not a hit in any assay (**Fig. 2B**).

Figure 2. (A) GPNMB TREAT-AD biological domain annotations and **(B)** phenotypes from CRISPR screens in iPSC derived cell types from the CRISPRbrain resource.

VALIDATED ANTIBODIES AND KNOCKOUT CELL LINES

YCharOS Antibody Characterization

The Antibody Characterization through Open Science (YCharOS) initiative, led from McGill University, is a global, public-good effort uniting academic researchers, funding agencies, 13 leading antibody manufacturers, and two knockout cell line providers. Using industry-endorsed protocols [17], YCharOS systematically evaluates antibody performance with the goal of identifying one or more high-quality renewable antibodies (e.g., monoclonal or recombinant) per human protein target. Antibodies are tested side-by-side in immunoblot (western blot), immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence using isogenic knockout cell lines as controls. All results are shared openly and rapidly via the AD Knowledge Portal

(<https://adknowledgeportal.synapse.org/>) and in the Zenodo YCharOS community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/treatad/>).

YCharOS has identified the U-87 MG cell line background with adequate GPNMB protein expression and GPNMB was KD using a pool of siRNA targeting this gene. YCharOS' partners contributed 20 GPNMB antibodies which were tested side-by-side by immunoblot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence. Renewable antibodies were found to be specific for all three applications. The antibody characterization report generated by YCharOS is available on Zenodo. Complete report: [GPNMB antibody characterization report](#) [18].

PROTEIN CONSTRUCTS AND EXPRESSION METHODS

Protein Purified

1. [GPNMBA-c000](#): Ectodomain of GPNMB (M1- N498) containing a C-terminal TEV cleavage site-His10-Twin strep tag. This protein will be useful for activity assays and crystallography.

Figure 3. (A) SEC trace of GPNMBA-c000 with **(B)** major peak fractions run on an SDS-PAGE gel.

See **Additional information (section 1)** with details of plasmid expression constructs and purification procedures.

CONCLUSION

GPNMB is a glycoprotein with physiological roles across central and peripheral tissues, with potential links to Alzheimer's disease (AD) progression through its impacts on autophagic function and amyloid plaque-associated microglia. Though the exact mechanisms by which GPNMB may be related to AD are unclear, evidence generally points to an increase in this protein's expression in neurodegenerative disease states, potentially representing a compensatory mechanism promoting neuroprotection [5,19]. A deeper investigation of these effects of GPNMB and its potential as a therapeutic target are warranted.

We present in this TEP a series of tools and reagents to facilitate investigations into GPNMB in AD. We report a Bioinformatic Analysis which positions GPNMB as a protein of high interest based on its Target Risk Score (98th percentile), partially driven by an increase in both RNA and protein expression in AD vs control samples. We next evaluated commercially available renewable antibodies specific for GPNMB, reporting

several with utility in immunoblot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence assays. Lastly, we developed and optimized a plasmid expression construct for the purification of GPNMB for the further testing and characterization of this protein of interest. The tools presented in this TEP provide a foundation for further biological investigation of the role of GPNMB in neurodegeneration and AD.

FUNDING INFORMATION

The work performed by the Emory-Sage-SGC TREAT-AD Center has been funded by the National Institute on Aging through grant U54AG065187.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Materials and Methods

1. Proteins Expression and Purification

All relevant plasmids are available on addgene: [TREAT-AD plasmid collection](#)

Expression host	<i>Mammalian</i> : Expi293F cells (Thermo Fisher Scientific)
Expression medium	FreeStyle 293 Expression Medium (Thermo Fisher Scientific)
BacMam virus generation	<p>For transposition, transform construct into the <i>E. coli</i> strain DH10Bac. Plate on LB-agar plates containing kanamycin (50 µg/ml), gentamycin (7 µg/ml), tetracycline (10 µg/ml), IPTG (40 µg/ml) and bluo-gal (300 µg/ml). Inoculate 5 ml LB broth containing kanamycin (50 µg/ml), gentamycin (7 µg/ml) and tetracycline (10 µg/ml) with a single colony and grow overnight at 37°C with shaking. Perform MiniPrep (Millipore) according to manufacturer’s instructions. Add 1 volume of isopropanol to precipitate the bacmid DNA. Spin (13000g, 20 min, 4°C) and wash pellet with 70% ethanol. Resuspend bacmid with sterile TE buffer under sterile conditions.</p> <p>Generate BacMam viruses by transfecting Sf9 cells.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Dilute Sf9 cells grown to mid-log phase to 2x10⁵ cells/ml in Sf-900 II SFM medium and dispense 1ml of cells into each well of a 24-well plate. Allow the cells to attach for 1 h at room temperature. 2. Mix 2 µl Insect GeneJuice with 40 µl Sf-900 II SFM medium per transfection. Add 2 µl bacmid DNA (at 0.1 – 2.0 µg/µl) and mix gently. Incubate for 15 min at room temperature. 3. Add 160 µl Sf-900 II SFM medium to the mix. 4. Aspirate medium from the cells and gently add the transfection mix from step 3. 5. Incubate cells for 4 h at 27°C in a humidified incubator. 6. Add 400 µl Sf-900 II SFM medium containing 2% FBS to each well. 7. Incubate cells at 27°C in a humidified incubator. 8. Harvest cell culture supernatant at 3 days post transfection (1500g, 20 min, room temperature). 9. Amplify the generated BacMam viruses as required.

Transduction	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Split Expi293F cells to 1×10^6 cells/ml in 500 ml FreeStyle 293 Expression Medium. Incubate for 24 h until cells are approximately 2×10^6 cells/ml (37°C, 150 rpm, 8% CO₂, 75% rh). 2. Add BacMam viruses (3% v/v, p2) directly to the cells. 3. Add sodium butyrate (1 M sterile stock) to 10 mM final concentration. 4. Incubate cells at 30°C (8%CO₂/75% rh) with shaking at 150 rpm. 5. Harvest cell culture supernatant at 3 days post transduction (900g, 20 min, 4°C). 6. Filter supernatant through 0.2 mm filter.
Purification buffers	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. W10 buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 10 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol 2. W30 buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 30 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol 3. Ni IMAC elution buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 300 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol 4. SEC buffer: 20 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 200 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol 5. Ni-sepharose beads, equilibrated in Ni IMAC W10 buffer.
Purification step 1: IMAC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Add imidazole to the filtered supernatant to 10 mM final concentration. 2. Add a total of 2.5 ml equilibrated Ni-sepharose beads to the cell supernatant, split into 50-ml falcon tubes. Mix by rotation for 1 hr in a cold room. 3. Spin beads/supernatant slurry (700g, 5 min, 4°C). Decant supernatant and wash beads with 100 ml W10 buffer. Repeat wash with 50 ml W10. Spin again and transfer beads to gravity column in a cold room. 4. Wash column with 25 ml W30. 5. Elute protein with 1x 10 ml elution buffer, followed by 2x5 ml elution buffer. Analyse the EB fractions by SDS-PAGE and determine the protein yield using the Bradford assay.
Purification step 2: Size-exclusion chromatography	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Concentrate the protein to 2 ml using a centrifugal concentrator with the appropriate MWCO. 2. Purify the protein further by Size-exclusion chromatography (SEC) on a HiLoad Superdex S200 HR 16/60 column in SEC buffer at 1 ml/min. 3. Analyse fractions by SDS-PAGE. Pool fractions containing protein of desired purity and concentrate to 2 mg/ml, as measured by UV spectroscopy. 4. Snap-freeze aliquots in thin-walled PCR tubes in liquid N₂, and store at -80°C.
Protein Yield	5 mg/L of culture

References

1. Murthy MN, Blauwendraat C, UKBEC, Guelfi S, IPDGC, Hardy J, et al. Increased brain expression of GPNMB is associated with genome wide significant risk for Parkinson's disease on chromosome 7p15.3. *Neurogenetics*. 2017;18: 121–133. doi:10.1007/s10048-017-0514-8
2. Sala Frigerio C, Wolfs L, Fattorelli N, Thrupp N, Voytyuk I, Schmidt I, et al. The major risk factors for Alzheimer's disease: Age, sex, and genes modulate the microglia response to A β plaques. *Cell Rep*. 2019;27: 1293–1306.e6. doi:10.1016/j.celrep.2019.03.099
3. Satoh J-I, Kino Y, Yanaizu M, Ishida T, Saito Y. Microglia express GPNMB in the brains of Alzheimer's disease and Nasu-Hakola disease. *Intractable Rare Dis Res*. 2019;8: 120–128. doi:10.5582/irdr.2019.01049
4. Wang H, Dey KK, Chen P-C, Li Y, Niu M, Cho J-H, et al. Integrated analysis of ultra-deep proteomes in cortex, cerebrospinal fluid and serum reveals a mitochondrial signature in Alzheimer's disease. *Mol Neurodegener*. 2020;15: 43. doi:10.1186/s13024-020-00384-6
5. Gillett DA, Wallings RL, Uriarte Huarte O, Tansey MG. Progranulin and GPNMB: interactions in endo-lysosome function and inflammation in neurodegenerative disease. *J Neuroinflammation*. 2023;20: 286. doi:10.1186/s12974-023-02965-w
6. Smith AM, Davey K, Tsartsalis S, Khozoie C, Fancy N, Tang SS, et al. Diverse human astrocyte and microglial transcriptional responses to Alzheimer's pathology. *Acta Neuropathol*. 2022;143: 75–91. doi:10.1007/s00401-021-02372-6
7. Saade M, Araujo de Souza G, Scavone C, Kinoshita PF. The role of GPNMB in inflammation. *Front Immunol*. 2021;12: 674739. doi:10.3389/fimmu.2021.674739
8. Murata K, Yoshino Y, Tsuruma K, Moriguchi S, Oyagi A, Tanaka H, et al. The extracellular fragment of GPNMB (Glycoprotein nonmelanosoma protein B, osteoactivin) improves memory and increases hippocampal GluA1 levels in mice. *J Neurochem*. 2015;132: 583–594. doi:10.1111/jnc.13010
9. Neal ML, Boyle AM, Budge KM, Safadi FF, Richardson JR. The glycoprotein GPNMB attenuates astrocyte inflammatory responses through the CD44 receptor. *J Neuroinflammation*. 2018;15. doi:10.1186/s12974-018-1100-1
10. Prabata A, Ikeda K, Rahardini EP, Hirata K-I, Emoto N. GPNMB plays a protective role against obesity-related metabolic disorders by reducing macrophage inflammatory capacity. *J Biol Chem*. 2021;297: 101232. doi:10.1016/j.jbc.2021.101232
11. Zhu Z, Liu Y, Li X, Zhang L, Liu H, Cui Y, et al. GPNMB mitigates Alzheimer's disease and enhances autophagy via suppressing the mTOR signal. *Neurosci Lett*. 2022;767: 136300. doi:10.1016/j.neulet.2021.136300
12. Yin Z, Raj D, Saiepour N, Van Dam D, Brouwer N, Holtman IR, et al. Immune hyperreactivity of A β plaque-associated microglia in Alzheimer's disease. *Neurobiol Aging*. 2017;55: 115–122. doi:10.1016/j.neurobiolaging.2017.03.021
13. Hüttenrauch M, Ogorek I, Klafki H, Otto M, Stadelmann C, Weggen S, et al. Glycoprotein NMB: a novel Alzheimer's disease associated marker expressed in a subset of activated microglia. *Acta Neuropathol Commun*. 2018;6: 108. doi:10.1186/s40478-018-0612-3
14. Cary GA, Wiley JC, Gockley J, Keegan S, Amirtha Ganesh SS, Heath L, et al. Genetic and multi-omic risk

assessment of Alzheimer's disease implicates core associated biological domains. *Alzheimers Dement (N Y)*. 2024;10: e12461. doi:10.1002/trc2.12461

15. Gabitto MI, Travaglini KJ, Rachleff VM, Kaplan ES, Long B, Ariza J, et al. Integrated multimodal cell atlas of Alzheimer's disease. *Nat Neurosci*. 2024;27: 2366–2383. doi:10.1038/s41593-024-01774-5
16. Tian R, Abarientos A, Hong J, Hashemi SH, Yan R, Dräger N, et al. Genome-wide CRISPRi/a screens in human neurons link lysosomal failure to ferroptosis. *Nat Neurosci*. 2021;24: 1020–1034. doi:10.1038/s41593-021-00862-0
17. Ayoubi R, Ryan J, Gonzalez Bolivar S, Alende C, Ruiz Moleon V, Fotouhi M, et al. A consensus platform for antibody characterization. *Nat Protoc*. 2025;20: 1509–1545. doi:10.1038/s41596-024-01095-8
18. Ayoubi R, Alende C, Fotouhi M, González Bolívar S, Ruiz Moleon V, Laflamme C. A guide to selecting high-performing antibodies for GPNMB (UniProt ID: Q14956) for use in western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence. 2025. doi:10.5281/ZENODO.16543752
19. Tsou P-S, Sawalha AH. Glycoprotein nonmetastatic melanoma protein B: A key mediator and an emerging therapeutic target in autoimmune diseases. *FASEB J*. 2020;34: 8810–8823. doi:10.1096/fj.202000651